

Studies on the Stability Constants of Vanadium-N-Cinnamoyl-N-Phenyl Hydroxylamine Complexes—A 1:2 Metal-Ligand System

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The stability constants of a 1 : 2 metal-ligand complex system have been evaluated spectrophotometrically by graphical extrapolation methods following Yatsimirskii's and Leden's ideas for calculation of K_1 and K_2 . For the present study we have selected N-Cinnamoyl-N-phenyl hydroxylamine as the most sensitive reagent among the arylhydroxylamine derivatives. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of the vanadium complexes are found to be 4.62 and 4.41 by Yatsimirskii's method and those by Leden's method are 4.81 and 4.74 respectively.

EARLIER investigators^{1,2} have utilized the stable violet coloured vanadium chelate for the detection and estimation of microgram quantities of the metal. The complex has got its absorption maximum at 540 nm. Recently, the over-all formation constant of the metal chelate has been reported³ following Harvey and Manning's⁴ method. Like most other arylhydroxylamine analogues, N-cinnamoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine is a bidentate ligand and forms complexes with metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 2, but the nature of absorbing species in solution has seldom been determined.

The present paper deals with spectrophotometric determination of stepwise formation constants of the vanadium-N-cinnamoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine complexes—a 1 : 2 metal-ligand system. The evaluation of formation constants has been made following Yatsimirskii's method^{5,6}. Leden's method⁷ of determining the 'degree of complex formation' has also been employed to determine the two stepwise stability constants. The stepwise formation constants values obtained by the above two methods agree fairly well with each other. The overall stability constants data have been compared with the reported values.

Experimental

Ammonium metavanadate solutions :

Standard vanadium solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium vanadate (Riedel-de Haen A.G.) in warm ammonia and then diluted to known volume by distilled water. The vanadium content of this solution was determined by complexometric titration with ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid using Eriochrome Black T as indicator. A standard solution of strength (0.75×10^{-3} mole/litre) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution containing 1.0 mg/ml vanadium

Reagent solutions :

The reagent was prepared from N-phenyl hydroxylamine and cinnamoyl chloride as described by Shome⁸

and was further purified by repeated recrystallization from benzene-pet. ether mixture. The m.p. of the compound was found to be 161° (sharp).

Standard reagent solutions of desired strength in alcohol-free spectro-grade chloroform were used and stored in amber coloured bottle.

Other chemicals and solvents used in all spectrophotometric measurements were G.R. or spectro-grade quality.

Apparatus :

A unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer with absorption cells of 1.00 cm light path were used for all photometric measurements.

Composition of the complex :

Equimolar solutions of vanadium and reagent (0.75×10^{-3} mole/litre) were utilised to find out metal to ligand ratio by Job's method of continuous variation⁹ and Mole-Ratio method⁴. The extractive photometric measurements made at 540 nm from 6N hydrochloric acid indicated a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 2.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot of vanadium (V) solution (0.75×10^{-3} mole/litre) was taken in a 100-ml separatory funnel and the acid concentration in the aqueous phase adjusted at 6N hydrochloric acid. Different amounts of equimolar reagent solution in alcohol-free chloroform was added in such a way that the total volume of the non-aqueous phase was always kept 10 ml at each step of the titration. The ratio of aqueous and non-aqueous phase was 1 : 1 and the mixture was then shaken for 5 mins to reach equilibrium. The violet chloroform layer was allowed to settle, separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phase was washed with a further 5 ml portion of chloroform. The combined

extract, after drying over sodium sulphate, was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform. Complex shows an absorption maximum at 540 nm when measured against solvent blank. The reagent blank obtained by the same procedure from 6*N* HCl has no absorption in the wavelength region 510–540 nm. Hence, chloroform as the blank was taken in all absorption measurements.

The vanadium complex is extractable into chloroform from 2 to 8 (*N*) hydrochloric acid with no appreciable change in sensitivity value. The molar absorptivity is 6300 ± 50 as calculated from Beer's Law.

Determination of stepwise formation constants:

The stepwise formation constants K_1 and K_2 of vanadium complexes ML_1 and ML_2 respectively were evaluated following graphical extrapolation method of Yatsimirskii^{5,6} and of Leden⁷. Several suitable subsidiary functions were constructed and the appropriate limiting values at zero-ligand concentrations were utilised to arrive at the result.

Yatsimirskii's method:

The calculations by this method were made with the help of following equations:

$$1) \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} f_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\bar{e}}{[L]} = a_1 = e_1\beta_1 - e_1\beta_1^i$$

$$2) \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} \bar{e} = b_1$$

$$3) \lim_{Y \rightarrow 0} g = \frac{\bar{e} - b_1}{Y} = b_2$$

where f, g = Subsidiary functions

a, b = Intercept values

$$Y = \frac{1}{[L]}$$

e = Extinction values.

Leden's method:

Formation constants values by this method were obtained from considerations of the following:

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = K_1$$

$$\lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \psi_2 = \lim_{[L] \rightarrow 0} \frac{\psi_1 - K_1}{[L]} = K_1 K_2$$

where ϕ = Degree of complex formation

ψ_1, ψ_2 = Subsidiary functions.

The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ obtained by the above two methods are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR THE VANADIUM-N-CINNAMOYL-N-PHENYL HYDROXYLAMINE (1:2 COMPOSITION) COMPLEX AT 25°

Method	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log K
Yatsimirskii	4.62	4.41	9.03
Leden's	4.81	4.74	9.55
Reported value ³	—	—	8.91

Results and Discussion

The stepwise formation constants were calculated from the extrapolated values of the subsidiary functions. From the established composition 1:2 (Metal:Ligand) the free-ligand concentration for each solution was calculated from Beer's Law data. The evaluation was possible even in the presence of insufficient (not stoichiometric amount) reagent where appreciable dissociation occurs. Here, we assumed that the absorbance corresponds mainly due to a mono-nuclear coloured complex species of vanadium.

In order to evaluate the two formation constants by Leden's method from spectrophotometric data a series of subsidiary functions were constructed and extrapolated to zero value of the variable $[L]$. The intercept values obtained leads to the calculation of K_1 and K_2 .

The calculated values of f_1 have been plotted against free-ligand at equilibrium, $[L]$ and extrapolated to 6 zero value of $[L]$. This gave a value of 2.2×10^8 for a_1 . A curved function was obtained near the stoichiometric point of titration where dissociation of the complex occurs. The extrapolation was necessary since the experimental points obtained from absorbance values corresponding to the free-ligand concentrations in the range 0 to 4×10^{-5} moles/litre indicated some deviations from the usual plot. Inherent experimental error led to deviations in the said range, as the absorbance values were sufficiently low in the region. Moreover, a change in f_1 value from 2.2×10^8 to $2.2 \pm 0.5 \times 10^8$ did not affect the result appreciably and $\log K_1$ or $\log K_2$ values remained within ± 0.1 . The function f_2 plotted against $[L]$ illustrates the linearity of the function and the intercept gave $a_2 = (-)2.6 \times 10^{12}$. The intercept indicates the theoretical molar extinction coefficient (e) for the vanadium oxo-chelate and yielded for b_1 the value of 6.21×10^3 . The corresponding 'e' value calculated from Beer's Law was found to be $(6.3 \pm 0.05) \times 10^3$. This suggests clearly that the extrapolation was in the right direction.

The plot of the function g against $[Y]$ gave $b_2 = (-)3.8 \times 10^{-2}$. Substituting the values of a_1, a_2, b_1 and b_2 ,

$$[a_1 = 2.2 \times 10^8, \quad a_2 = (-)2.6 \times 10^{12}$$

$$b_1 = 6.21 \times 10^3 \text{ and } b_2 = (-)3.8 \times 10^{-2}]$$

the value for K_1 was found to be 4.2×10^4 and K_2 turned out to be 2.55×10^4 .

TABLE 2

Metal = Reagent = $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$; Acidity in aq. phase = $6N$ HCl; Solvent = $CHCl_3$; Final volume = 25 ml, Absorbance for metal conc. $3.925 \times 10^{-5} M = 0.235$; Metal taken = 3 ml of $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$. $\lambda_{max} = 540$ nm.

Solution	Total ligand Conc. moles/ litre ($C_L \times 10^5$)	Absorbance	Free-ligand Conc. moles/ litre ($[L] \times 10^5$)	Molar Extinction ($e \times 10^{-3}$)	$f_1 \times 10^{-8}$	$f_2 \times 10^{-12}$	$Y \times 10^{-4}$	$g \times 10^2$
1	18	0.480	1.970	5.333	2.707	—	5.076	-1.728
2	21	0.495	4.468	5.500	1.232	-2.169	2.239	-3.173
3	24	0.515	6.800	5.722	0.8416	-1.997	1.471	-3.318
4	27	0.530	9.298	5.888	0.6333	-1.685	1.075	-2.994
5	30	0.335	12.130	5.944	0.4900	-1.409	0.824	-3.227

— = Not used in constructing plots in Figs. because of great deviation.

TABLE 3

Absorbance for metal conc. $3.925 \times 10^{-5} M = 0.235$

Total metal conc. = $9.0 \times 10^{-5} M (= C_M)$

Solution	Absorbance	Total ligand conc. mole/ litre ($C_L \times 10^5$)	Conc. of metal complexed, mole/litre ($\times 10^5$)	Free-ligand conc., moles/ litre ($[L] \times 10^5$)	Free-metal conc., moles/ litre ($[M] \times 10^5$)	Degree of complex formation, $\varphi = \frac{C_M}{[M]}$	ψ_1 ($\times 10^{-5}$)	ψ_2 ($\times 10^{-9}$)
1	0.045	3	0.7515	1.497	8.249	1.09	0.061	—
2	0.180	6	3.006	—	5.994	1.50	—	—
3	0.220	9	3.673	1.654	5.327	1.69	0.042	—
4	0.305	12	5.093	1.814	3.907	2.30	0.718	—
5	0.390	15	6.513	1.974	2.487	3.62	1.326	3.425
6	0.480	18	8.015	1.970	0.985	9.14	4.130	—
7	0.495	21	8.266	4.468	0.734	12.26	2.520	4.185
8	0.515	24	8.600	6.800	0.400	22.50	3.161	3.693
9	0.530	27	8.851	9.298	0.149	60.39	6.389	6.173
10	0.535	30	8.935	12.130	0.065	138.50	11.330	8.802

— = Not used in constructing plots in Figs. because of great deviation.

The molar absorptivity e_1 , e_2 for the species ML_1 and ML_2 are 5.23×10^3 and 6.21×10^3 respectively.

In the Leden's method of calculation ψ_1 is plotted as the ordinate and $[L]$ as the abscissa, function ψ_1 reduces to β_1 when $[L] = 0$. The constant β_1 was found practically by extrapolation of the function ψ_1 as the intercept. The first formation constant β_1 for the 1 : 1 complex or K_1 was found to be 6.5×10^4 . The plot of ψ_2 against $[L]$ gave on extrapolation the intercept β_2 , the overall, formation constant for 1 : 2 composition or $K_1 K_2 = 3.6 \times 10^9$. So, K_2 turns out to be 5.53×10^4 . The results are tabulated in Tables 2 and 3.

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